

Laser-stimulated birefringence of Ga₂O₃-La₂S_{2.95}Se_{0.05} glasses for optical recording of information

A.M. El Naggar^{a,*}, A.A. Albassam^a, G. Lakshminarayana^{b,*}, Dong-Eun Lee^{c,*}, Jonghun Yoon^{d,*}, Taejoon Park^{e,*}, I.V. Kityk^{f,h}, P. Czaja^f, M. Nowak^f, E. Gondek^{g,h}

^a Research Chair of Exploitation of Renewable Energy Applications in Saudi Arabia, Physics & Astronomy Department, College of Science, King Saud University, P.O. Box 2455, 11451 Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

^b Intelligent Construction Automation Center, Kyungpook National University, 80, Daehak-ro, Buk-gu, Daegu 41566, Republic of Korea

^c School of Architecture and Civil Engineering, Kyungpook National University, 80, Daehak-ro, Buk-gu, Daegu 41566, Republic of Korea

^d Department of Mechanical Engineering, Hanyang University, 55 Hanyangdaehak-ro, Ansan, Gyeonggi-do 15588, Republic of Korea

^e Department of Robotics Engineering, Hanyang University, 55 Hanyangdaehak-ro, Ansan, Gyeonggi-do 15588, Republic of Korea

^f Institute of Optoelectronics and Measuring Systems, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czestochowa University of Technology, 17 Armii Krajowej Str., 42-200 Czestochowa, Poland

^g Institute of Physics, Cracow University of Technology, ul. Podchorążych 1, 30-084 Kraków, Poland

^h Department of Inorganic and Physical Chemistry, Eastern European National University, Lutsk, Ukraine

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Optoelectronic materials
Chalcogenide glasses
Laser-induced effects
Birefringence
Electronic and electrical engineering

ABSTRACT

We show an opportunity to change the birefringence of Ga₂O₃ – La₂S_{2.95}Se_{0.05} glasses doped by Er³⁺ and La³⁺ ions at λ = 1150 nm wavelength of cw He-Ne laser under illumination of the femtosecond laser. The variation of the refractive indices was found during illumination by 180 fs laser with frequency about 65 MHz (at wavelength λ = 1045 nm). The laser-stimulated birefringence has been explored versus temperature. The observed laser induced and temperature dependences of the birefringence confirm a huge contribution of anharmonic phonon subsystems which is typical for chalcogenide glasses. Due to an occurrence of local space charge density asymmetry, the efficiency of birefringence is enhanced. The anisotropy effect exists only during the illumination and is diminished during 10...12 s after switching off of the photo-inducing laser treatment. There is observed also a correlation between the occurred grating patterns and the values of the birefringence.

Introduction

Recently one can see an enhanced interest in exploring the chalcogenide materials due to the existence of significant light stimulated optical effects [1–3]. These effects are useful for the application in broadband gradient index optics [4], photonics [5], Mid-infrared super-continuum generation [6], optical fiber systems [7], and nonlinear optical waveguides [8]. Particular interest here present rare-earth (RE)-doped chalcogenide glasses [9,10] due to promising opportunities for operation by local polarizabilities and nonlinear optical hyper-polarizabilities. Moreover, among the RE-doped chalcogenide glasses, exceptional interest present Er³⁺ and La³⁺ ions [11–14].

In this work, we explore the photo-induced changes of birefringence (at 1150 nm) for new fabricated Ga₂O₃ – La₂S_{2.95}Se_{0.05} glasses doped by Er and La ions under the influence of the coherent femtosecond laser beams at λ = 1045 nm. We will explore the laser-induced optical

constants versus the femtosecond laser coherent beam power for two types of glasses doped by La and Er (0.5% in weighting units). This may be of particular interest for application in photonics. Additionally, a separate interest may present a grating formation, which may be used for optimization of the photonic crystals.

Experimental

Fabrication of glasses

We have used Ga₂O₃ (99.99% purity) and La₂S_{2.95}Se_{0.3} prepared from La₂O₃ (purity 99.9%) by sulfidizing-selenization at 920–998 °C. The mixture of La₂S_{2.95}Se_{0.3} and Ga₂O₃ in 1:1.3–1:4 ratio and in 1:1.7 ratio doped by Er and La has been taken in vitreous carbon crucibles containing inside a silica ampoules and it was heated up to 1110–1370 °C for sulfur evaporation during 1.5 h. Afterward, the

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: elnaggar@ksu.edu.sa (A.M. El Naggar), gandham@knu.ac.kr (G. Lakshminarayana), dolee@knu.ac.kr (D.-E. Lee), yooncsmd@gmail.com (J. Yoon), taejoon@hanyang.ac.kr (T. Park).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2019.102349>

Received 18 March 2019; Received in revised form 11 May 2019; Accepted 11 May 2019

Available online 17 May 2019

2211-3797/ © 2019 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Fig. 1. Principal set-up for the measurements of photoinduced-laser patterning.

ampoules were cooled with a temperature rate of 0.5 K/min and subsequently annealed at 450–500 °C during 2 h. A total mass of the glass was equal to about 7 g. From “as annealed” glasses, parallelepiped plates with dimension up to 20 mm and a thickness equal to about 1 mm were prepared for the measurements. The surfaces of the plates were parallel to each other and were treated first by Al_2O_3 abrasive for polishing and next by diamond paste.

The specimens for optical spectroscopy had a form of parallelepipeds with a thickness of about 0.8 mm. The specimens have been polished using fine-grained abrasive powder. Subsequently, the surface of the plates was polished with a paste, which allows to obtain irregularities with the roughness not exceeding 1 μm .

Measurements of the birefringence and the space gratings efficiencies versus the fundamental laser energy density were performed using the set-up presented in Fig. 1. The set-up possesses two optical channels (see Fig. 1). The first one is formed by 180 fs laser source with frequency 65 MHz ($\lambda = 1045 \text{ nm}$) and pulse energy equal to about 15 nJ. The beam diameter was equal to about 1.2 mm. These photo-inducing beams have been split for two channels with a different intensity ratio of the incident beams. The time of the treatment has been controlled by optical fiber through the changes of the absorption. Simultaneously, it was monitored by the photo-destruction of the samples and changes of temperature. The measurements of the birefringence have been done using the cw He-Ne laser (wavelength 1150 nm) at a power about 25 mW with a beam diameter varying within the 1.8... 2.2 mm) for TEM_{00} mode. The one-mode beam has been analyzed using the traditional Senarmont scheme with an accuracy of the birefringence determination equal to about 10^{-5} .

During the measurements of the birefringence, the laser-stimulated femtosecond beam was split into two incident beams at angles varying within 21 ... 27°. In order to avoid some space non-homogeneity of the photo-inducing beams of the samples. The measurements have been carried out in more than 30 points of the specimen samples. This one allowed us to achieve the necessary accuracy using sufficient statistics. The energy power has been changed using a set of polarizers P and mirrors M possessing dichroic films. Simultaneously, with the two-beam treatment, the dc-electric field with frequency about 1 MHz was applied to form some assisted alignments. The beam-splitters allowed us to perform the control of the laser power density. This regime of the coherent laser treatment was carried out before the measurements of the birefringence only, and the photo-induced treatment was continued up to 2...3 min and stabilization of the gratings was monitored by the CCD (see Fig. 1). The birefringence measurement was performed immediately (a few microseconds) after coherent laser illumination. The

signal has decreased seconds without any irreversible effects.

The maximally tuned energy density of the p-polarized light was equal to about 130 J/m^2 . The further increase was limited by the photo-thermal destruction of the samples. The value of the fundamental radiation was monitored by the germanium detector.

The studied parallelepiped glasses were placed on a rotary table with an optical cryostat in a special cover. The photodetectors and the measuring table engine were connected to a PC computer. The entire measuring set-up was placed under the blackout box eliminating the influence of external electromagnetic radiation.

Temperature dependences of laser-stimulated birefringence have been controlled simultaneously. Samples were mounted inside the optical cryostat and the measurements of birefringence were carried out within the temperature range 77–350 K.

Results and discussion

Laser-stimulated birefringence

Typical dependences of the birefringence and grating patterns at different ratio are presented in Fig. 2(a)–(c), respectively.

One can clearly see that contrary to the light polarization and the RE content the gratings are very sensitive to the intensity ratio of the two coherent photo-inducing beams.

It is necessary to emphasize that these gratings are almost identical for the La-doped samples. Moreover, these gratings have existed at least 10 s after the treatment.

The origin of the grating patterns is closely connected with the modulation of the optical functions causing changes of absorption (see Fig. 3). It should be clarified that the presented data mean only the changes of the absorption and not the absolute values. The picture is almost identical for both types of the gratings and is closely related to the observed space distributions of the profile (see Fig. 2). At the same time, the birefringence demonstrated a clear dependence on the RE doping (see Fig. 4). One can see that for La-doped glasses it is significantly lower than that of the Er. This is clear from Fig. 3, where we can observe an occurrence of the absorption gratings. All the laser treatment does not give any irreversible changes what was controlled by optical polarimetry method

The presented data unambiguously shows that the addition of Er and La ions changes an enhanced laser-stimulated birefringence. More interesting is that with temperature the behavior of the birefringence is quite different. This fact may be explained by a huge role of phonon subsystem, which is different for the Er and La ions. Generally, it may

Fig. 2. (a). Photo-induced gratings patterns formed by two coherent laser beams with intensity ratio 1:1 for Er-doped samples Fig. 2. (b). Photo-induced grating patterns created by two coherent laser beams with ratio 1:4 for Er-doped samples Fig. 2. (c). Photo-induced gratings created by the two coherent laser beams with ratio 1:7 for Er-doped samples.

Fig. 2. (continued)

Fig. 2. (continued)

Fig. 3. Space distribution of the changes of absorption detected by He-Ne cw laser light.

Fig. 4. Dependence of the birefringence in the 10^{-4} for the optimal values of the temperature.

be observed only in the chalcogenides due to huge anharmonic phonons, shown by the linear and nonlinear optical studies [15–17]. We have explored also the laser stimulated piezo-optics as well as electro-optics and the corresponding magnitudes did not exceed 0.4% with respect to the basic values. The additional control of the multi-photon excitation did not give a significant contribution (below 3%).

We have done the same experiments for the oxide glasses like $\text{PbO-BiO}_{1.5}\text{-GaO}_{1.5}$ and crystals such as BiB_3O_6 possessing high nonlinear optical features with RE ions [18–21]. For these materials both in the glass as well as in the crystalline form, the corresponding photo-induced effects have been not observed including with the temperature changes. So the role of the phonon anharmonicities for the chalcogenides may also play a primary role here [22].

Conclusions

We have demonstrated an opportunity to vary the refractive indices during the illumination by 180 fs laser with frequency repetition about 65 MHz (at wavelength $\lambda = 1045$ nm). During the measurements of the birefringence, the laser-stimulated femtosecond beam formed into two incident beams at angles varying between 21 and 27°. The laser-stimulated birefringence was examined with respect to temperature changes. We have found that contrary to the light polarization and the

RE content, the gratings are very sensitive to the ratio of the two coherent photo-inducing beams. It is necessary to emphasize that these gratings have been almost identical for the La-doped samples. Moreover, these gratings have existed at least 10 s after the treatment.

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to the Deanship of Scientific Research, King Saud University for funding through Vice Deanship of Scientific Research Chairs. For Prof. Kityk, this work is a part of a project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 778156. For authors Dr. G.L.N., Prof. Lee, Prof. Yoon, and Prof. Park, this work was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) grant funded by the Korea government (MSIT) (No. NRF-2018R1A5A1025137).

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rinp.2019.102349>.

References

- [1] Du Q, Luo Z, Zhong H, Zhang Y, Huang Y, Du T, et al. Chip-scale broadband spectroscopic chemical sensing using an integrated supercontinuum source in a chalcogenide glass waveguide. *Photon. Res.* 2018;6:506–10.
- [2] Li C, Novak S, Denisov SA, McClenaghan ND, Patel N, Agarwal A, et al. Electro spray deposition of quantum dot-doped $\text{Ge}_{23}\text{Sb}_7\text{S}_{70}$ chalcogenide glass films. *Thin Solid Films* 2017;626:194–9.
- [3] Sisken L, Smith C, Buff A, Kang M, Chamma K, Wachtel P, et al. Evidence of spatially selective refractive index modification in $15\text{GeSe}_2\text{-}45\text{As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-}40\text{PbSe}$ glass ceramic through correlation of structure and optical property measurements for GRIN applications. *Opt. Mater. Exp.* 2017;7:3077–92.
- [4] Kang M, Swisher AM, Pogrebnyakov AV, Liu L, Kirk A, Aiken S, et al. Ultra-low dispersion multicomponent thin film chalcogenide glass for broadband gradient index optics. *Adv. Mater.* 2018;30:1803628.
- [5] Yadav A, Kang M, Goncalves C, Sisken L, Blanco C, Arias C, Richardson K. Index and dispersion engineering of $\text{GeSe}_2\text{-As}_2\text{Se}_3\text{-PbSe}$ chalcogenide glasses through purification. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc.* 2018. submitted.
- [6] Karim MR, Rahman BMA, Agrawal GP. Mid-infrared supercontinuum generation using dispersion-engineered $\text{Ge}_{11.5}\text{As}_{24}\text{Se}_{64.5}$ chalcogenide channel waveguide. *Opt. Exp.* 2015;23:6903–14.
- [7] Møller U, Yu Y, Kubat I, Petersen CR, Gai X, Brilland L, et al. Multi-milliwatt mid-infrared supercontinuum generation in a suspended core chalcogenide fiber. *Opt. Exp.* 2015;23:3282–91.
- [8] Almeida JMP, Barbano EC, Arnold CB, Misoguti L, Mendonça CR. Nonlinear optical waveguides in $\text{As}_2\text{S}_3\text{-Ag}_2\text{S}$ chalcogenide glass thin films. *Opt. Mater. Exp.* 2017;7:93–9.
- [9] Buff A. A Study of Crystallization Behavior in Phase Separated Chalcogenide Glasses PhD. Thesis Orlando, FL, USA: University of Central Florida; 2016.
- [10] Halyan VV, Kityk IV, Kevshyn AH, Ivashchenko IA, Lakshminarayana G, Shevchuk MV, et al. Effect of temperature on the structure and luminescence properties of $\text{Ag}_{0.05}\text{Ga}_{0.05}\text{Ge}_{0.95}\text{S}_2\text{-Er}_2\text{S}_3$ glasses. *J. Lumin.* 2017;181:315–20.
- [11] Sario MD, Mescia L, Prudeniano F, Smektala F, Deseveday F, Nazabal V, et al. Feasibility of Er^{3+} -doped, $\text{Ga}_5\text{Ge}_{20}\text{Sb}_{10}\text{S}_{65}$ chalcogenide microstructured optical fiber amplifiers. *Opt. Laser Technol.* 2009;41:99–106.
- [12] Tahmasebi Z, Hatami M. Study of the gain saturation effect on the propagation of dark soliton in Er^{3+} -doped, $\text{Ga}_5\text{Ge}_{20}\text{Sb}_{10}\text{S}_{65}$ chalcogenide fiber amplifier. *Opt. Commun.* 2011;284:656–9.
- [13] Loireau-Lozac'h A-M, Guittard M, Flahaut J. Verres formes par les sulfures 12_53 des terres rares avec le sulfure de gallium Ga_2S_3 . *Mater. Res. Bull.* 1976;11:1489–96.
- [14] Loireau-Lozac'h A-M, Guittard M, Flahaut J. Systèmes $12_53\text{-Ga}_2\text{S}_3$ (L = La, Ce, Dy, Er et Y) diagrammes de phases. *Mater. Res. Bull.* 1997;12:881–6.
- [15] Kityk IV. IR-stimulated second harmonic generation in $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_2\text{Se-BaF}_2\text{-PbCl}_2$ glasses. *J. Modern Opt.* 2004;51:1179–89.
- [16] Kityk IV. IR-induced second harmonic generation in $\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_3\text{-BaF}_2\text{-PbCl}_2$ glasses. *J. Phys. Chem. B* 2003;107:10083–7.
- [17] Shpotyuk OI, Kasperczyk J, Kityk IV. Mechanism of reversible photoinduced optical effects in amorphous As_2S_3 . *J. Non-Cryst. Solids* 1997;215:218–25.
- [18] Kityk IV, Golis E, Fihpecki J, Wasylak J, Zacharko VM. Photoinduced nonlinear optical phenomena in $\text{PbO-BiO}_{1.5}\text{-GaO}_{1.5}$ glass. *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.* 1995;14:1292–3.
- [19] Kityk IV, Wasylak J, Dorosz J, Kucharski J. Eu^{3+} -doped glass materials for red luminescence. *Opt. Laser Technol.* 2001;33:157–60.
- [20] Brenier A, Kityk IV. Spectroscopic properties of Pr^{3+} -doped $\text{Ca}_4\text{GdO}(\text{BO}_3)_3$ (GdCOB). *J. Appl. Phys.* 2001;90:232–6.
- [21] Brenier A, Kityk IV, Majchrowski A. Evaluation of Nd^{3+} -doped BiB_3O_6 (BIBO) as a new potential self-frequency conversion laser crystal. *Opt. Commun.* 2002;203:125–32.
- [22] Theerthagiri J, Senthil RA, Senthilkumar B, Polu AR, Madhavan J, Ashokkumar M. Recent advances in MoS_2 nanostructured materials for energy and environmental applications – a review. *J. Solid State Chem.* 2017;252:43–71.